

Neutrosophic quadruple ideals in neutrosophic quadruple BCI-algebras

G. Muhiuddin¹, Florentin Smarandache², Young Bae Jun^{3,*}

¹Department of Mathematics, University of Tabuk, Tabuk 71491, Saudi Arabia.

E-mail: chishtygm@gmail.com

²Mathematics & Science Department, University of New Mexico, 705 Gurley Ave., Gallup, NM 87301, USA.

E-mail: fsmarandache@gmail.com

³Department of Mathematics Education, Gyeongsang National University, Jinju 52828, Korea.

E-mail: skywine@gmail.com

*Correspondence: Young Bae Jun (skywine@gmail.com)

Abstract: In the present paper, we discuss the Neutrosophic quadruple q -ideals and (regular) neutrosophic quadruple ideals and investigate their related properties. Also, for any two nonempty subsets U and V of a BCI-algebra S , conditions for the set $NQ(U, V)$ to be a (regular) neutrosophic quadruple ideal and a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of a neutrosophic quadruple BCI-algebra $NQ(S)$ are discussed. Furthermore, we prove that let U, V, I and J be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that $I \subseteq U$ and $J \subseteq V$. If I and J are q -ideals of S , then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Keywords: neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-number, neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-algebra, (regular) neutrosophic quadruple ideal, neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal.

1 Introduction

To deal with incomplete, inconsistent and indeterminate information, Smarandache introduced the notion of neutrosophic sets (see ([1], [2] and [3])). In fact, neutrosophic set is a useful mathematical tool which extends the notions of classic set, (intuitionistic) fuzzy set and interval valued (intuitionistic) fuzzy set. Neutrosophic set theory has useful applications in several branches (see for e.g., [4], [5], [6] and [7]).

In [8], Smarandache considered an entry (i.e., a number, an idea, an object etc.) which is represented by a known part (a) and an unknown part (bT, cI, dF) where T, I, F have their usual neutrosophic logic meanings and a, b, c, d are real or complex numbers, and then he introduced the concept of neutrosophic quadruple numbers. Neutrosophic quadruple algebraic structures and hyperstructures are discussed in [9] and [10]. Recently, neutrosophic set theory has been applied to the BCK/BCI-algebras on various aspects (see for e.g., [11], [12] [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19] and [20].) Using the notion of neutrosophic quadruple numbers based on a set, Jun et al. [21] constructed neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-algebras. They investigated several properties, and considered ideal and positive implicative ideal in neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra, and closed

ideal in neutrosophic quadruple BCI-algebra. Given subsets A and B of a neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-algebra, they considered sets $NQ(U, V)$ which consists of neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-numbers with a condition. They provided conditions for the set $NQ(U, V)$ to be a (positive implicative) ideal of a neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra, and the set $NQ(U, V)$ to be a (closed) ideal of a neutrosophic quadruple BCI-algebra. They gave an example to show that the set $\{\tilde{0}\}$ is not a positive implicative ideal in a neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra, and then they considered conditions for the set $\{\tilde{0}\}$ to be a positive implicative ideal in a neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra. Muhiuddin et al. [22] discussed several properties and (implicative) neutrosophic quadruple ideals in (implicative) neutrosophic quadruple BCK -algebras.

In this paper, we introduce the notions of (regular) neutrosophic quadruple ideal and neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal in neutrosophic quadruple BCI-algebras, and investigate related properties. Given nonempty subsets A and B of a BCI-algebra S , we consider conditions for the set $NQ(U, V)$ to be a (regular) neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$ and a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

2 Preliminaries

We begin with the following definitions and properties that will be needed in the sequel.

A nonempty set S with a constant 0 and a binary operation $*$ is called a BCI-algebra if for all $x, y, z \in S$ the following conditions hold ([23] and [24]):

$$(I) \quad (((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0),$$

$$(II) \quad ((x * (x * y)) * y = 0),$$

$$(III) \quad (x * x = 0),$$

$$(IV) \quad (x * y = 0, y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y).$$

If a BCI-algebra S satisfies the following identity:

$$(V) \quad (\forall x \in S) (0 * x = 0),$$

then S is called a BCK -algebra. Define a binary relation \leq on X by letting $x * y = 0$ if and only if $x \leq y$. Then (S, \leq) is a partially ordered set.

Theorem 2.1. *Let S be a BCK/BCI-algebra. Then following conditions are hold:*

$$(\forall x \in S) (x * 0 = x), \tag{2.1}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in S) (x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z, z * y \leq z * x), \tag{2.2}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in S) ((x * y) * z = (x * z) * y), \tag{2.3}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in S) ((x * z) * (y * z) \leq x * y) \tag{2.4}$$

where $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Any BCI-algebra S satisfies the following conditions (see [25]):

$$(\forall x, y \in S) (x * (x * (x * y)) = x * y), \tag{2.5}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in S) (0 * (x * y) = (0 * x) * (0 * y)), \tag{2.6}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in S) (0 * (0 * (x * y)) = (0 * y) * (0 * x)). \tag{2.7}$$

A nonempty subset A of a BCK/BCI-algebra S is called a *subalgebra* of S if $x * y \in A$ for all $x, y \in A$. A subset I of a BCK/BCI-algebra S is called an *ideal* of S if it satisfies:

$$0 \in I, \tag{2.8}$$

$$(\forall x \in S) (\forall y \in I) (x * y \in I \Rightarrow x \in I). \tag{2.9}$$

An ideal I of a BCI-algebra S is said to be *regular* (see [26]) if it is also a subalgebra of S .

It is clear that every ideal of a BCK-algebra is regular (see [26]).

A subset I of a BCI-algebra S is called a *q-ideal* of S (see [27]) if it satisfies (2.8) and

$$(\forall x, y, z \in S)(x * (y * z) \in I, y \in I \Rightarrow x * z \in I). \tag{2.10}$$

We refer the reader to the books [25, 28] for further information regarding BCK/BCI-algebras, and to the site “<http://fs.gallup.unm.edu/neutrosophy.htm>” for further information regarding neutrosophic set theory.

We consider neutrosophic quadruple numbers based on a set instead of real or complex numbers.

Definition 2.2 ([21]). Let S be a set. A *neutrosophic quadruple S-number* is an ordered quadruple (a, xT, yI, zF) where $a, x, y, z \in S$ and T, I, F have their usual neutrosophic logic meanings.

The set of all neutrosophic quadruple S -numbers is denoted by $NQ(S)$, that is,

$$NQ(S) := \{(a, xT, yI, zF) \mid a, x, y, z \in S\},$$

and it is called the *neutrosophic quadruple set* based on S . If S is a BCK/BCI-algebra, a neutrosophic quadruple S -number is called a *neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-number* and we say that $NQ(S)$ is the *neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-set*.

Let S be a BCK/BCI-algebra. We define a binary operation \otimes on $NQ(S)$ by

$$(a, xT, yI, zF) \otimes (b, uT, vI, wF) = (a * b, (x * u)T, (y * v)I, (z * w)F)$$

for all $(a, xT, yI, zF), (b, uT, vI, wF) \in NQ(S)$. Given $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 \in S$, the neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-number (a_1, a_2T, a_3I, a_4F) is denoted by \tilde{a} , that is,

$$\tilde{a} = (a_1, a_2T, a_3I, a_4F),$$

and the zero neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-number $(0, 0T, 0I, 0F)$ is denoted by $\tilde{0}$, that is,

$$\tilde{0} = (0, 0T, 0I, 0F).$$

We define an order relation “ \ll ” and the equality “ $=$ ” on $NQ(S)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{x} \ll \tilde{y} &\Leftrightarrow x_i \leq y_i \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \\ \tilde{x} = \tilde{y} &\Leftrightarrow x_i = y_i \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3, 4 \end{aligned}$$

for all $\tilde{x}, \tilde{y} \in NQ(S)$. It is easy to verify that “ \ll ” is an equivalence relation on $NQ(S)$.

Theorem 2.3 ([21]). *If S is a BCK/BCI-algebra, then $(NQ(S); \otimes, \tilde{0})$ is a BCK/BCI-algebra.*

We say that $(NQ(S); \otimes, \tilde{0})$ is a *neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-algebra*, and it is simply denoted by $NQ(S)$.

Let S be a BCK/BCI-algebra. Given nonempty subsets A and B of S , consider the set

$$NQ(U, V) := \{(a, xT, yI, zF) \in NQ(S) \mid a, x \in U \ \& \ y, z \in V\},$$

which is called the *neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set*.

The set $NQ(U, U)$ is denoted by $NQ(U)$, and it is called the *neutrosophic quadruple U -set*.

3 (Regular) neutrosophic quadruple ideals

Definition 3.1. Given nonempty subsets U and V of a BCI-algebra S , if the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a (regular) ideal of a neutrosophic quadruple BCI-algebra $NQ(S)$, we say $NQ(U, V)$ is a (regular) *neutrosophic quadruple ideal* of $NQ(S)$.

Question 1. *If U and V are subalgebras of a BCI-algebra S , then is the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ a neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$?*

The answer to Question 1 is negative as seen in the following example.

Example 3.2. Consider a BCI-algebra $S = \{0, 1, a, b, c\}$ with the binary operation $*$, which is given in Table 1. Then the neutrosophic quadruple BCI-algebra $NQ(S)$ has 625 elements. Note that $U = \{0, a\}$ and $V = \{0, b\}$

Table 1: Cayley table for the binary operation “ $*$ ”

$*$	0	1	a	b	c
0	0	0	a	b	c
1	1	0	a	b	c
a	a	a	0	c	b
b	b	b	c	0	a
c	c	c	b	a	0

are subalgebras of S . The neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ consists of the following elements:

$$NQ(U, V) = \{\tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \tilde{3}, \tilde{4}, \tilde{5}, \tilde{6}, \tilde{7}, \tilde{8}, \tilde{9}, \tilde{10}, \tilde{11}, \tilde{12}, \tilde{13}, \tilde{14}, \tilde{15}\}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{0} &= (0, 0T, 0I, 0F), \tilde{1} = (0, 0T, 0I, bF), \tilde{2} = (0, 0T, bI, 0F), \\ \tilde{3} &= (0, 0T, bI, bF), \tilde{4} = (0, aT, 0I, 0F), \tilde{5} = (0, aT, 0I, bF), \\ \tilde{6} &= (0, aT, bI, 0F), \tilde{7} = (0, aT, bI, bF), \tilde{8} = (a, 0T, 0I, 0F), \\ \tilde{9} &= (a, 0T, 0I, bF), \tilde{10} = (a, 0T, bI, 0F), \tilde{11} = (a, 0T, bI, bF), \\ \tilde{12} &= (a, aT, 0I, 0F), \tilde{13} = (a, aT, 0I, bF), \\ \tilde{14} &= (a, aT, bI, 0F), \tilde{15} = (a, aT, bI, bF). \end{aligned}$$

If we take $(1, aT, bI, 0F) \in NQ(S)$, then $(1, aT, bI, 0F) \notin NQ(U, V)$ and

$$(1, aT, bI, 0F) \otimes \tilde{9} = \tilde{15} \in NQ(U, V).$$

Hence the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is not a neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$.

We consider conditions for the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ to be a regular neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Lemma 3.3 ([21]). *If U and V are subalgebras (resp., ideals) of a BCI-algebra S , then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple subalgebra (resp., ideal) of $NQ(S)$.*

Theorem 3.4. *Let U and V be subalgebras of a BCI-algebra S such that*

$$(\forall x, y \in S)(x \in U \text{ (resp., } V), y \notin U \text{ (resp., } V) \Rightarrow y * x \notin U \text{ (resp., } V)). \tag{3.1}$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a regular neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Proof. By Lemma 3.3, $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple subalgebra of $NQ(S)$. Hence it is clear that $\tilde{0} \in NQ(U, V)$. Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \in NQ(S)$ and $\tilde{y} = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F) \in NQ(S)$ be such that $\tilde{y} \otimes \tilde{x} \in NQ(U, V)$ and $\tilde{x} \in NQ(U, V)$. Then $x_i \in U$ and $x_j \in V$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $j = 3, 4$. Also,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y} \otimes \tilde{x} &= (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F) \otimes (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \\ &= (y_1 * x_1, (y_2 * x_2)T, (y_3 * x_3)I, (y_4 * x_4)F) \in NQ(U, V), \end{aligned}$$

and so $y_1 * x_1 \in U$, $y_2 * x_2 \in U$, $y_3 * x_3 \in V$ and $y_4 * x_4 \in V$. If $\tilde{y} \notin NQ(U, V)$, then $y_i \notin A$ or $y_j \notin B$ for some $i = 1, 2$ and $j = 3, 4$. It follows from (3.1) that $y_i * x_i \notin U$ or $y_j * x_j \notin V$ for some $i = 1, 2$ and $j = 3, 4$. This is a contradiction, and so $\tilde{y} \in NQ(U, V)$. Thus $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$, and therefore $NQ(U, V)$ is a regular neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$. \square

Corollary 3.5. *Let U be a subalgebra of a BCI-algebra S such that*

$$(\forall x, y \in S)(x \in U, y \notin U \Rightarrow y * x \notin U). \tag{3.2}$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple U -set $NQ(U)$ is a regular neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Theorem 3.6. *Let U and V be subsets of a BCI-algebra S . If any neutrosophic quadruple ideal $NQ(U, V)$ of $NQ(S)$ satisfies $\tilde{0} \otimes \tilde{x} \in NQ(U, V)$ for all $\tilde{x} \in NQ(U, V)$, then $NQ(U, V)$ is a regular neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$.*

Proof. For any $\tilde{x}, \tilde{y} \in NQ(U, V)$, we have

$$(\tilde{x} \otimes \tilde{y}) \otimes \tilde{x} = (\tilde{x} \otimes \tilde{x}) \otimes \tilde{y} = \tilde{0} \otimes \tilde{y} \in NQ(U, V).$$

Since $NQ(U, V)$ is an ideal of $NQ(S)$, it follows that $\tilde{x} \otimes \tilde{y} \in NQ(U, V)$. Hence $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple subalgebra of $NQ(S)$, and therefore $NQ(U, V)$ is a regular neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$. \square

Corollary 3.7. *Let U be a subset of a BCI-algebra S . If any neutrosophic quadruple ideal $NQ(U)$ of $NQ(S)$ satisfies $\tilde{0} \otimes \tilde{x} \in NQ(U)$ for all $\tilde{x} \in NQ(U)$, then $NQ(U)$ is a regular neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$.*

Table 2: Cayley table for the binary operation “*”

*	0	1	<i>a</i>
0	0	0	<i>a</i>
1	1	0	<i>a</i>
<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	0

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{1}2 &= (1, 1T, 0I, 0F), \tilde{1}3 = (1, 1T, 0I, 1F), \\ \tilde{1}4 &= (1, 1T, 1I, 0F), \tilde{1}5 = (1, 1T, 1I, 1F). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.3. For any nonempty subsets *U* and *V* of a BCI-algebra *S*, if the neutrosophic quadruple (*U, V*)-set *NQ(U, V)* is a neutrosophic quadruple *q*-ideal of *NQ(S)*, then it is both a neutrosophic quadruple subalgebra and a neutrosophic quadruple ideal of *NQ(S)*.

Proof. Assume that *NQ(U, V)* is a neutrosophic quadruple *q*-ideal of *NQ(S)*. Since $\tilde{0} \in NQ(U, V)$, we have $0 \in U$ and $0 \in V$. Let $x, y, z \in S$ be such that $x * (y * z) \in U \cap V$ and $y \in U \cap V$. Then $(y, yT, yI, yF) \in NQ(U, V)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} &(x, xT, xI, xF) \otimes ((y, yT, yI, yF) \otimes (z, zT, zI, zF)) \\ &= (x, xT, xI, xF) \otimes (y * z, (y * z)T, (y * z)I, (y * z)F) \\ &= (x * (y * z), (x * (y * z))T, (x * (y * z))I, (x * (y * z))F) \in NQ(U, V). \end{aligned}$$

Since *NQ(U, V)* is a neutrosophic quadruple *q*-ideal of *NQ(S)*, it follows that

$$(x * z, (x * z)T, (x * z)I, (x * z)F) = (x, xT, xI, xF) \otimes (z, zT, zI, zF) \in NQ(U, V).$$

Hence $x * z \in U \cap V$, and therefore *U* and *V* are *q*-ideals of *S*. Since every *q*-ideal is both a subalgebra and an ideal, it follows from Lemma 3.3 that *NQ(U, V)* is both a neutrosophic quadruple subalgebra and a neutrosophic quadruple ideal of *NQ(S)*. □

The converse of Theorem 4.3 is not true as seen in the following example.

Example 4.4. Consider a BCI-algebra $S = \{0, a, b, c\}$ with the binary operation $*$, which is given in Table 3.

Table 3: Cayley table for the binary operation “*”

*	0	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>
0	0	<i>c</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>a</i>
<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	0	<i>c</i>	<i>b</i>
<i>b</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>a</i>	0	<i>c</i>
<i>c</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>a</i>	0

Then the neutrosophic quadruple BCI-algebra $NQ(S)$ has 256 elements. If we take $A = \{0\}$ and $B = \{0\}$, then $NQ(U, V) = \{\tilde{0}\}$ is both a neutrosophic quadruple subalgebra and a neutrosophic quadruple ideal of $NQ(S)$. If we take $\tilde{x} := (c, bT, 0I, aF)$, $\tilde{z} := (a, bT, 0I, cF) \in NQ(S)$, then

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{x} \otimes (\tilde{0} \otimes \tilde{z}) &= (c, bT, 0I, aF) \otimes (\tilde{0} \otimes (a, bT, 0I, cF)) \\ &= (c, bT, 0I, aF) \otimes (c, bT, 0I, aF) = \tilde{0} \in NQ(U, V).\end{aligned}$$

But

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{x} \otimes \tilde{z} &= (c, bT, 0I, aF) \otimes (a, bT, 0I, cF) \\ &= (c * a, (b * b)T, (0 * 0)I, (a * c)F) \\ &= (b, 0T, 0I, bF) \notin NQ(U, V).\end{aligned}$$

Therefore $NQ(U, V)$ is not a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

We provide conditions for the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ to be a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal.

Theorem 4.5. *If U and V are q -ideals of a BCI-algebra S , then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.*

Proof. Suppose that U and V are q -ideals of a BCI-algebra S . Obviously, $\tilde{0} \in NQ(U, V)$. Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F)$, $\tilde{y} = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F)$ and $\tilde{z} = (z_1, z_2T, z_3I, z_4F)$ be elements of $NQ(S)$ be such that $\tilde{x} \otimes (\tilde{y} \otimes \tilde{z}) \in NQ(U, V)$ and $\tilde{y} \in NQ(U, V)$. Then $y_i \in A$, $y_j \in B$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $j = 3, 4$, and

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{x} \otimes (\tilde{y} \otimes \tilde{z}) &= (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \otimes ((y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F) \otimes (z_1, z_2T, z_3I, z_4F)) \\ &= (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \otimes (y_1 * z_1, (y_2 * z_2)T, (y_3 * z_3)I, (y_4 * z_4)F) \\ &= (x_1 * (y_1 * z_1), (x_2 * (y_2 * z_2))T, (x_3 * (y_3 * z_3))I, (x_4 * (y_4 * z_4))F) \\ &\in NQ(U, V),\end{aligned}$$

that is, $x_i * (y_i * z_i) \in U$ and $x_j * (y_j * z_j) \in B$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $j = 3, 4$. It follows from (2.10) that $x_i * z_i \in U$ and $x_j * z_j \in V$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $j = 3, 4$. Thus

$$\tilde{x} \otimes \tilde{z} = (x_1 * z_1, (x_2 * z_2)T, (x_3 * z_3)I, (x_4 * z_4)F) \in NQ(U, V), \quad (4.1)$$

and therefore $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$. □

Corollary 4.6. *If A is a q -ideal of a BCI-algebra S , then the neutrosophic quadruple U -set $NQ(U)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.*

Corollary 4.7. *If $\{0\}$ is a q -ideal of a BCI-algebra S , then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$ for any ideals U and V of S .*

Corollary 4.8. *If $\{0\}$ is a q -ideal of a BCI-algebra S , then the neutrosophic quadruple U -set $NQ(U)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$ for any ideal U of S .*

Theorem 4.9. *Let U and V be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that*

$$(\forall x, y, z \in S)(x * (y * z) \in U \cap V \Rightarrow (x * y) * z \in U \cap V). \tag{4.2}$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Proof. It is clear that $\tilde{0} \in NQ(U, V)$. Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F)$, $\tilde{y} = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F)$ and $\tilde{z} = (z_1, z_2T, z_3I, z_4F)$ be elements of $NQ(S)$ be such that $\tilde{x} \otimes (\tilde{y} \otimes \tilde{z}) \in NQ(U, V)$ and $\tilde{y} \in NQ(U, V)$. Then $y_1, y_2 \in U, y_3, y_4 \in V$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{x} \otimes (\tilde{y} \otimes \tilde{z}) &= (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \otimes ((y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F) \otimes (z_1, z_2T, z_3I, z_4F)) \\ &= (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \otimes (y_1 * z_1, (y_2 * z_2)T, (y_3 * z_3)I, (y_4 * z_4)F) \\ &= (x_1 * (y_1 * z_1), (x_2 * (y_2 * z_2))T, (x_3 * (y_3 * z_3))I, (x_4 * (y_4 * z_4))F) \\ &\in NQ(U, V), \end{aligned}$$

that is, $x_i * (y_i * z_i) \in U$ and $x_j * (y_j * z_j) \in V$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $j = 3, 4$. It follows from (2.3) and (4.2) that $(x_i * z_i) * y_i = (x_i * y_i) * z_i \in U$ and $(x_j * z_j) * y_j = (x_j * y_j) * z_j \in V$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $j = 3, 4$. Since U and V are ideals of S , we have $x_i * z_i \in U$ and $x_j * z_j \in V$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $j = 3, 4$. Thus

$$\tilde{x} \otimes \tilde{z} = (x_1 * z_1, (x_2 * z_2)T, (x_3 * z_3)I, (x_4 * z_4)F) \in NQ(U, V), \tag{4.3}$$

and therefore $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$. □

Corollary 4.10. *Let U be an ideal of a BCI-algebra S such that*

$$(\forall x, y, z \in S)(x * (y * z) \in U \Rightarrow (x * y) * z \in U). \tag{4.4}$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple U -set $NQ(U)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Theorem 4.11. *Let U and V be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that*

$$(\forall x, y \in S)(x * (0 * y) \in U \cap V \Rightarrow x * y \in U \cap V). \tag{4.5}$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Proof. Assume that $x * (y * z) \in U \cap V$ for all $x, y, z \in S$. Note that

$$\begin{aligned} ((x * y) * (0 * z)) * (x * (y * z)) &= ((x * y) * (x * (y * z))) * (0 * z) \\ &\leq ((y * z) * y) * (0 * z) \\ &= (0 * z) * (0 * z) = 0 \in U \cap V \end{aligned}$$

Thus $(x * y) * (0 * z) \in U \cap V$ since U and V are ideals of S . It follows from (4.9) that $(x * y) * z \in U \cap V$. Using Theorem 4.9, $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$. □

Corollary 4.12. *Let U be an ideal of a BCI-algebra S such that*

$$(\forall x, y \in S)(x * (0 * y) \in U \Rightarrow x * y \in U). \tag{4.6}$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple U -set $NQ(U)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Theorem 4.13. *Let U and V be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that*

$$(\forall x, y \in S)(x \in U \cap V \Rightarrow x * y \in U \cap V). \quad (4.7)$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Proof. Assume that $x * (y * z) \in U \cap V$ and $y \in U \cap V$ for all $x, y, z \in S$. Using (2.3) and (4.7), we get $(x * z) * (y * z) = (x * (y * z)) * z \in U \cap V$ and $y * z \in U \cap V$. Since U and V are ideals of S , it follows that $x * z \in U \cap V$. Hence U and V are q -ideals of S , and therefore $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$ by Theorem 4.5. \square

Corollary 4.14. *Let U be an ideal of a BCI-algebra S such that*

$$(\forall x, y \in S)(x \in U \Rightarrow x * y \in U). \quad (4.8)$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple U -set $NQ(U)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Theorem 4.15. *Let U, V, I and J be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that $I \subseteq U$ and $J \subseteq V$. If I and J are q -ideals of S , then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.*

Proof. Let $x, y, z \in S$ be such that $x * (0 * y) \in U \cap V$. Then

$$(x * (x * (0 * y))) * (0 * y) = (x * (0 * y)) * (x * (0 * y)) = 0 \in I \cap J$$

by (2.3) and (III). Since I and J are q -ideals of S , it follows from (2.3) and (2.10) that

$$(x * y) * (x * (0 * y)) = (x * (x * (0 * y))) * y \in I \cap J \subseteq U \cap V$$

Since U and V are ideals of S , we have $x * y \in U \cap V$. Therefore $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$ by Theorem 4.11. \square

Corollary 4.16. *Let U and I be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that $I \subseteq U$. If I is a q -ideal of S , then the neutrosophic quadruple U -set $NQ(U)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.*

Theorem 4.17. *Let U, V, I and J be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that $I \subseteq U$, $J \subseteq V$ and*

$$(\forall x, y, z \in S)(x * (y * z) \in I \cap J \Rightarrow (x * y) * z \in I \cap J). \quad (4.9)$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Proof. Let $x, y, z \in S$ be such that $x * (y * z) \in I \cap J$ and $y \in I \cap J$. Then

$$(x * z) * y = (x * y) * z \in I \cap J$$

by (2.3) and (4.9). Since I and J are ideals of S , it follows that $x * z \in I \cap J$. This shows that I and J are q -ideals of S . Therefore $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$ by Theorem 4.15. \square

Corollary 4.18. *Let U and I be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that $I \subseteq U$ and*

$$(\forall x, y, z \in S)(x * (y * z) \in I \Rightarrow (x * y) * z \in I). \quad (4.10)$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple U -set $NQ(U)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Theorem 4.19. Let U, V, I and J be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that $I \subseteq U, J \subseteq V$ and

$$(\forall x, y \in S)(x \in I \cap J \Rightarrow x * y \in I \cap J). \quad (4.11)$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Proof. By the proof of Theorem 4.13, we know that I and J are q -ideals of S . Hence $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$ by Theorem 4.15. \square

Corollary 4.20. Let U and I be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that $I \subseteq U$ and

$$(\forall x, y \in S)(x \in I \Rightarrow x * y \in I). \quad (4.12)$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple A -set $NQ(U)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Theorem 4.21. Let U, V, I and J be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that $I \subseteq U, J \subseteq V$ and

$$(\forall x, y \in S)(x * (0 * y) \in I \cap J \Rightarrow x * y \in I \cap J). \quad (4.13)$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Proof. Assume that $x * (y * z) \in I \cap J$ For all $x, y, z \in S$. Then $(x * y) * z \in I \cap J$ by the proof of Theorem 4.11. It follows from Theorem 4.17 that neutrosophic quadruple (U, V) -set $NQ(U, V)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$. \square

Corollary 4.22. Let U and I be ideals of a BCI-algebra S such that $I \subseteq U$ and

$$(\forall x, y \in S)(x * (0 * y) \in I \Rightarrow x * y \in I). \quad (4.14)$$

Then the neutrosophic quadruple U -set $NQ(U)$ is a neutrosophic quadruple q -ideal of $NQ(S)$.

Future Work: Using the results of this paper, we will apply it to another algebraic structures, for example, MV-algebras, BL-algebras, MTL-algebras, R_0 -algebras, hoops, (ordered) semigroups and (semi, near) rings etc.

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References

- [1] F. Smarandache, Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Probability, Set, and Logic, ProQuest Information & Learning, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA, 105 p., 1998. <http://fs.gallup.unm.edu/eBook-neutrosophics6.pdf> (last edition online).
- [2] F. Smarandache, A Unifying Field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic. Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Probability, American Reserch Press, Rehoboth, NM, 1999.

- [3] F. Smarandache, Neutrosophic set-a generalization of the intuitionistic fuzzy set, *Int. J. Pure Appl. Math.* **24** (2005), no.3, 287–297.
- [4] Mohamed Abdel Basset, Victor Chang, Abdullallah Gamal, Florentin Smarandache, An integrated neutrosophic ANP and VIKOR method for achieving sustainable supplier selection: A case study in importing field, *Computers in Industry* **106**, 94-110 (2019).
- [5] Mohamed Abdel-Basset, M. Saleh, Abdullallah Gamal, Florentin Smarandache, An approach of TOPSIS technique for developing supplier selection with group decision making under type-2 neutrosophic number, *Applied Soft Computing* **77**, 438-452 (2019).
- [6] Mohamed Abdel-Basset, Gunasekaran Manogaran, Abdullallah Gamal, Florentin Smarandache, A Group Decision Making Framework Based on Neutrosophic TOPSIS Approach for Smart Medical Device Selection, *J. Medical Systems* **43**(2), 38:1-38:13 (2019).
- [7] Mohamed Abdel-Basset, Gunasekaran Manogaran, Abdullallah Gamal, Florentin Smarandache, A hybrid approach of neutrosophic sets and DEMATEL method for developing supplier selection criteria, *Design Autom. for Emb. Sys.* **22**(3), 257-278 (2018).
- [8] F. Smarandache, Neutrosophic quadruple numbers, refined neutrosophic quadruple numbers, absorbance law, and the multiplication of neutrosophic quadruple numbers, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, **10** (2015), 96–98.
- [9] A.A.A. Agboola, B. Davvaz and F. Smarandache, Neutrosophic quadruple algebraic hyperstructures, *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.* **14** (2017), no. 1, 29–42.
- [10] S.A. Akinleye, F. Smarandache and A.A.A. Agboola, On neutrosophic quadruple algebraic structures, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **12** (2016), 122–126.
- [11] G. Muhiuddin, S. J. Kim and Y. B. Jun, Implicative N-ideals of BCK-algebras based on neutrosophic N-structures, *Discrete Mathematics, Algorithms and Applications*, Vol. **11**, No. 01 (2019), 1950011.
- [12] G. Muhiuddin, H. Bordbar, F. Smarandache, Y. B. Jun, Further results on (\in, \in) -neutrosophic subalgebras and ideals in BCK/BCI-algebras, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. **20** (2018), 36-43.
- [13] A. Borumand Saeid and Y.B. Jun, Neutrosophic subalgebras of BCK/BCI-algebras based on neutrosophic points, *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.* **14** (2017), no. 1, 87–97.
- [14] Y.B. Jun, Neutrosophic subalgebras of several types in BCK/BCI-algebras, *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.* **14** (2017), no. 1, 75–86.
- [15] Y.B. Jun, S.J. Kim and F. Smarandache, Interval neutrosophic sets with applications in BCK/BCI-algebra, *Axioms* 2018, 7, 23.
- [16] Y.B. Jun, F. Smarandache and H. Bordbar, Neutrosophic \mathcal{N} -structures applied to BCK/BCI-algebras, *Information* 2017, 8, 128.
- [17] Y.B. Jun, F. Smarandache, S.Z. Song and M. Khan, Neutrosophic positive implicative \mathcal{N} -ideals in BCK/BCI-algebras, *Axioms* 2018, 7, 3.
- [18] M. Khan, S. Anis, F. Smarandache and Y.B. Jun, Neutrosophic \mathcal{N} -structures and their applications in semigroups, *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.* **14** (2017), no. 6, 583–598.
- [19] M.A. Öztürk and Y.B. Jun, Neutrosophic ideals in BCK/BCI-algebras based on neutrosophic points, *J. Inter. Math. Virtual Inst.* **8** (2018), 1–17.
- [20] S.Z. Song, F. Smarandache and Y.B. Jun, Neutrosophic commutative \mathcal{N} -ideals in BCK-algebras, *Information* 2017, 8, 130.
- [21] Y.B. Jun, S.Z. Song, F. Smarandache and H. Bordbar, Neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-algebras, *Axioms* 2018, 7, 41, doi:10.3390/axioms7020041

- [22] G. Muhiuddin, A.N. Al-Kenani, E.H. Roh and Y.B. Jun, Implicative neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebras and ideals, *Symmetry* 2019, 11, 277, doi:10.3390/sym11020277.
- [23] K. Iséki, On BCI-algebras, *Math. Seminar Notes* **8** (1980), 125–130.
- [24] K. Iséki and S. Tanaka, An introduction to the theory of BCK-algebras, *Math. Japon.* **23** (1978), 1–26.
- [25] Y. Huang, BCI-algebra, Science Press, Beijing, 2006.
- [26] Z.M. Chen and H.X. Wang, On ideals in BCI-algebras, *Math. Japon.* **36** (1991), no. 3, 497-501.
- [27] Y.L. Liu, J. Meng, X.H. Zhang and Z.C. Yue, q-ideals and a-ideals in BCI-algebras, *Southeast Asian Bulletin of Mathematics* **24** (2000), 243–253.
- [28] J. Meng and Y. B. Jun, BCK-algebras, Kyungmoonsa Co. Seoul, Korea 1994.

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